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Lasers – It's Role in Periodontal Regeneration

Princy Anna Mathew, Vikram More and B.S.Jagadish Pai

Coorg Institute of Dental Sciences , Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

The use of lasers has evolved as clinical experience along with scientific investigation. The dental lasers of today have benefited from decades of laser research and have their basis in certain theories from the field of quantum mechanics. When used efficaciously and ethically, lasers are an exceptional modality of treatment for many clinical conditions that dental specialists treat on a daily basis. The concept of using lasers for the treatment of periodontal disease elicits very strong reactions from all sides of spectrum. Evidence suggests that lasers are useful as an adjunct or alternative to traditional approaches in periodontal therapy. Future direction of lasers would be towards a minimally invasive regenerative procedures along with laser assisted calculus detection systems using laser fluorescence that is optical coherence tomography and a laser system which selectively and completely removes the plaque and calculus that is under development. With recent advances and development of wide range of laser wavelengths, different instrument designs and different delivery systems, the purpose of this review is to determine the application and current concept of lasers in the regeneration of periodontal tissues.

KEYWORDS

Carbon Dioxide Laser, Solid state Laser, Laser Assisted New Attachment Procedure, Laser assisted Comprehensive Pocket Treatment, Low Level Laser Therapy.

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